

CRM-GEOTHERMAL DELIVERABLE D2.5

REPORT ON RESOURCE CALCULATION ACCORDING TO THE UNFC

Summary:

Deliverable on the reporting of resources according to the UNFC template adaptation to joint heat and raw materials extraction.

Authors:

János Szanyi, University of Miskolc, Senior Researcher
Tamás Madarász, University of Miskolc, Associate Professor

Contributors:

W. Eberhard Falck, INTRAW, President
Vitor Correia, INTRAW, Secretary general
Christopher A. Rochelle, British Geological Survey, senior geochemist
Anna Seres, University of Miskolc, research fellow
Éva Hartai, University of Miskolc, honorary professor

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ORCID:	János Szanyi: 0000-0002-8053-6360 Tamás Madarász: 0000-0002-3291-1605		
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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Table of contents	3
Figures	3
Tables	4
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	5
2 Introduction.....	6
3 UNFC-2009 code - basic definitions.....	7
4 UNFC assessment process	9
5 Benefits and Challenges of applying the UNFC Framework to Joint Geothermal Energy Utilisation and CRM Extraction	10
6 Joint UNFC-assessment based on case study.....	12
6.1 Concept and calculation of the project	12
6.2 Assessment of electricity and heat resources according to the UNFC code.....	16
6.2.1 G axes – Geothermal resource quantification.....	17
6.2.2 E axes – Heat resource evaluation.....	19
6.2.3 F axes – Heat resource evaluation.....	19
6.2.4 E axes – Electricity resource evaluation	20
6.2.5 F axes – Electricity resource evaluation	20
6.3 Joint evaluation of electricity and heat resources according to the UNFC code	20
7 Assessment of Lithium resources according to the UNFC code.....	22
7.1.1 G axes – Lithium resource quantification	24
7.1.2 E axes – Lithium resource evaluation.....	25
7.1.3 F axes – Lithium resource evaluation.....	25
8 Conclusions	25
9 References.....	26
Appendix 1: E–axis decision tree (UNFC-Geothermal, 2022).....	29
Appendix 2: F–axis decision tree (UNFC-Geothermal, 2022).....	30
Appendix 3: G–axis decision tree (UNFC-Geothermal, 2022).....	31

FIGURES

Figure 1: UNFC-2009 classes (UNFC-Minerals, 2021)	9
Figure 2: The topography of the Pre-Cenozoic basement surroundings of Battonya High (Kun et al. 2022a).	13
Figure 3: Hydrostratigraphic units of the Battonya High (Horizontal extent: 70 km, vertical extent: 5 km (Figure 2 shows the section line; the thickness of the layers is not to scale) Legend: 1. Paleozoic metamorphic rocks, granite (Battonya Complex), 2. Lower and Middle Triassic fractured sandstone and dolomite, 3. Middle Miocene conglomerate, 4. Late Miocene conglomerate, 5. Late Miocene aleuritic marl, 6. Late Miocene turbidite, 7. Late Miocene delta sediments, 8. Quaternary formations. (Kun et al. 2022a).	14
Figure 4: Trapezium fuzzy numbers (a); triangular fuzzy numbers (b); (horizontal axis is the measured parameter; vertical axis membership value) (Kun et al. 2022b).	15

Figure 5: Temperature-time diagram showing 50 years of production (5000 m³/d) and 50 years of shutdown under two different scenarios (blue: worst case, orange: best case, L: distance between production and reinjection wells)..... 16

Figure 6: The referred project's UNFC fingerprint prior to drilling (Mijnlieff et al. 2019).. 17

Figure 7: UNFC classes and sub-classes to present combined or regional portfolio assessments (Falcone et al. 2025). 21

Figure 8: Volumetric delineation of various raw materials. A) Ore body; B) Hydrocarbon deposit; C) Subsurface complex flow system in ore rock. 23

Figure 9: Flowpath and simulated travel time in case of a geothermal dublet (Kun et al. 2022b). 23

TABLES

Table 1: The total amount of energy extracted and the values suitable for heat utilisation and power generation, according to different probability levels. 18

Table 2: The amount of energy that can be converted into electricity according to different probability levels. 19

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report uses a case study to demonstrate how the UNFC-2009 reporting standards can be adopted to the co-generation of electricity and heat with CRM (critical raw materials). This helps to link to work package 4 of the CRM-geothermal project, which focuses on 'The application of CRM and combined energy recovery from geothermal fluids'.

The joint application of the UNFC classification system to geothermal energy utilisation and CRM extraction offers considerable benefits for project integration, investment confidence, and sustainable resource governance. Although challenges remain - especially in aligning resource maturity levels and operational timelines - UNFC's flexibility and comprehensive scope make it a valuable tool for current and future hybrid resource developments.

According to the case study and laboratory tests carried out as part of the CRM-Geothermal Project, one of the most important things to examine is the kinetics of the process under reservoir conditions, i.e. how quickly the minerals lining the fractures dissolve.

In general, hydrodynamic and transport modelling are appropriate tools for the overall evaluation of the multiple projects according to the UNFC code. The joint assessment must be based on the value of each commodity, which is calculated separately according to its UNFC code. However, it must also assess the environmental, social and technical feasibility of all products. In all cases, the weakest category should be considered the common value. From an economic point of view, it should be considered whether the project as a whole can still be considered economically viable if the production of heat and electricity alone makes it viable, despite a possibly uneconomic nature of CRM production.

It is important to note that large datasets, particularly those from hydrocarbon research, facilitate the application of a wide range of machine learning methods. This is particularly true of comprehensive petrophysical datasets and traditional geostatistical methods that were previously carried out using them. As the calculation of recoverable geothermal energy is similar to that in the hydrocarbon industry in many respects, a breakthrough in the application of machine learning is expected soon.

2 INTRODUCTION

Geothermal energy is a reliable, weather-independent and locally available energy source that is partially renewable. It is a combination of rock, fluid and a heat source. Although it is ubiquitous in the Earth's crust, extracting it requires a carrier medium that is easily recoverable, has a high specific energy content, is cheap, and is available in large quantities (Szanyi and Antics, 2024).

Using geothermal energy can have significant economic and environmental benefits, particularly for heating and cooling purposes. However, the growth of the geothermal energy sector is lagging behind that of other renewable energies, particularly solar and wind (Rybach, 2010). One way to help address this, is to also extract critical raw materials (CRMs) from the geothermal fluids. Moreover, utilising geothermal brines for mineral extraction could provide a more sustainable and environmentally friendly alternative to traditional mining practices (Szanyi et al. 2023). The 'CRM-geothermal' project aims to open up a potentially huge untapped resource of CRM-rich geothermal fluids and deploy solutions to help Europe fulfil the strategic objectives of the EU Green Deal and the Agenda for Sustainable Development.

Clearly, different types of energy carrier, including both fossil and renewable, are competing with each other. Therefore, there is an increasing demand for the comparison of various energy resources and for asset classification systems. In response to this, the United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE) developed a classification framework for fossil energy and mineral reserves and assets called UNFC-2009 (the United Nations Framework Classification for Fossil Energy and Mineral Reserves and Resources, 2009), which was later extended to include renewable energy (UNECE, 2016). This framework allows for the harmonisation and comparison of mineral resource management activities and business processes, while also complying with financial reporting standards.

According to the updated supplementary specifications for applying the UNFC to geothermal energy resources (UNFC-Geothermal 2022), where a project delivers more than one geothermal energy product (e.g. heat and electricity), the corresponding geothermal energy resources have to be estimated and classified separately, but included in a single project report. Quantities of different geothermal energy products cannot be aggregated. Other products, such as CRMs (e.g. silica, lithium, manganese and zinc) and gases (e.g. carbon dioxide), may be classified according to other relevant UNFC specifications. These would then be combined in an overall evaluation, which would weigh potentially conflicting conclusions and/or emphasise synergistic aspects.

This report uses a case study to demonstrate how the UNFC-2009 reporting standards can be adopted to the co-generation of electricity and heat with CRM (critical raw materials). This helps to link to work package 4 of the CRM-geothermal project, which focuses on 'The application of CRM and combined energy recovery from geothermal fluids'.

3 UNFC-2009 CODE - BASIC DEFINITIONS

This report uses Beardsmore's terminology of the UNFC, defining the terms 'source', 'resource', 'known' and 'potential' as outlined in Beardsmore (2024): „A reference to a geothermal energy ‘source’ in this paper means a volume of underground rocks, sediments and pore fluids containing thermal energy which is available for extraction and/or conversion into process heat or electricity. Geoscientists might think of a ‘source’ as a subsurface reservoir of heat. A reference to a geothermal energy ‘resource’ means the total quantity of process heat or electricity that a project will produce over its lifetime. The emphasis here is on actual energy to be produced and utilised at the Earth’s surface, considering all recoverability and energy conversion processes. The word ‘known’ used in this paper in reference to a geothermal energy source means that the ability to commercially produce geothermal energy from the source has been established beyond reasonable doubt through testing, sampling and/or production. The word ‘potential’, however, means that the existence of recoverable energy and the commerciality of geothermal energy production has not yet been established.”

Separate UNFC supplementary specifications exist for mineral resources and geothermal energy sources (UNFC-Minerals 2021, UNFC-Geothermal 2022). The primary purpose of using the UNFC-2009 code in both cases is to calculate the resource stock associated with a given project according to different classes. The key difference is that geothermal energy is renewable, whereas resources found in mines are not. In other words, mineral resources are static, whereas geothermal energy requires dynamic stock calculations. Nevertheless, the principle is similar in both cases, as shown by the UNFC classification of geothermal energy.

The classification process involves identifying projects associated with geothermal energy sources and estimating the amount of energy that can be extracted and transferred as geothermal energy products from each project, taking into account the potential for regeneration. In the context of geothermal energy, a project encompasses all the systems and equipment connecting the energy resource to the point at which the final products are sold, used, transferred or disposed of. This includes all the necessary equipment and systems to extract and/or convert the energy, such as production and injection wells, ground or surface heat exchangers, interconnecting pipelines, energy conversion systems, and any necessary ancillary equipment. A project in the early stages of planning can only be defined conceptually. More mature projects, where some investment has already been made, need to be defined in greater detail. The reference point is a defined location in the production chain where the geothermal energy product is measured or estimated, usually at the point where the energy is sold to third parties or where it is transferred to the entity's utilisation department. Another important datum is the project lifetime, which should be reported together with the estimated energy quantities and the basis for their determination. If a project

produces more than one geothermal energy product (e.g., heat and electricity), the geothermal energy products that can be produced are estimated separately but reported together.

The UNFC-2009 classification system has three dimensions, because the evaluation of the project based on three fundamental criteria:

- environmental-socio-economic viability (E),
- technical feasibility (F),
- degree of confidence in the estimate (G)

The first dimension describes the socio-economic viability of the project, including the regulatory environment and environmental aspects (E-axis). The second dimension describes the status and feasibility of the project, including the availability of technology (F-axis). The third dimension describes the reliability of geological knowledge (G-axis) (Figure 1). The defined (quantified) amount of raw material or energy can be characterised by a three-digit code based on these factors (categories E, F and G), and this code can be used anywhere in the world in a consistent manner (Nádor, 2016). The definitions of each category and subcategory are summarised in Figure 1., the Appendices 1, 2, and 3. UNFC-2009 deliberately avoids the terms 'resource' and 'reserves' as their definitions becomes redundant in the new system. As the quantity of assets classified in Category G refers to the quantity available/exploitable from the assessment date until project completion, the E, F and G categories will vary, depending on the assessment date. For each of the three axes, categories (e.g. E1, E2, E3) and sometimes subcategories (e.g. E1.1) can be defined. A class may be defined as a combination of categories, sub-categories, or groups of categories from the three axes. As the code numbers always follow the same sequence (EFG), the letters can be omitted (e.g. 121 stands for E1, F2 and G1; Sári et al., 2013).

Figure 1: UNFC-2009 classes (UNFC-Minerals, 2021)

Several case studies on the use of the UNFC-2009 code have been conducted in relation to geothermal energy (Falcone et al. 2025). Meanwhile, the main effort with regard to mineral resources has focused on translating market-recognised assessment procedures into the UNFC-2009 code.

4 UNFC ASSESSMENT PROCESS

The classification process involves defining the geothermal project, estimating the amount of energy that can be extracted and converted into energy products, and determining the quantity of minerals that can be extracted from the fluid, namely:

1. defining a project - determining the source of the geothermal energy and the type of end products (heat, electricity + metal)
2. estimating the quantities of energy and metal that can be recovered and delivered as 'products' by the given project
3. classifying the quantified geothermal energy and metal resources based on the criteria defined by the E, F and G (sub-)categories.

As previously stated, for projects yielding multiple geothermal energy products, the relevant geothermal energy products should be estimated and categorised individually, with the results being reported collectively in a single project report. Other products, including materials, may be classified according to other relevant UNFC requirements. These should then be combined in an overall assessment.

5 BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES OF APPLYING THE UNFC FRAMEWORK TO JOINT GEOTHERMAL ENERGY UTILISATION AND CRM EXTRACTION

The increasing strategic importance of CRMs, alongside the rising demand for renewable energy such as geothermal power, is driving innovative co-extraction approaches. These developments necessitate robust and harmonised resource classification systems to assess technical, environmental, social, and economic viability. The UNFC offers a promising approach for integrated reporting and decision-making, particularly when applied jointly to geothermal energy and CRM recovery. It is reasonable to discern two scenarios when applying UNFC code to joint production: (1) when geothermal operations are already in place and CRM extraction is added later, and (2) when both components are developed concurrently. Additionally, we appreciate how UNFC-based joint classification supports financial and feasibility analysis for project stakeholders.

UNFC is a multi-sector classification framework capable of integrating assessments of both energy (e.g., geothermal) and mineral resources (e.g., lithium) under a unified model, accounting for the technological maturity, societal acceptance, policy constraints, and financial risk factors of each project component. In contrast, Committee for Mineral Reserves International Reporting Standards (CRIRSCO) aligned codes (e.g., Pan European Reserves and Resources Reporting Committee (PERC), Joint Ore Reserves Committee (JORC), National Instrument 51-101 Standards of Disclosure For Oil and Gas Activities (NI43-101)) focus more narrowly on minerals and are not designed for non-mineral energy resources such as geothermal. Thus, while CRIRSCO-compliant reporting is important for industry-specific investor communication, UNFC offers interoperability for multi-resource developments and allows non-viable resources to classify, contrary to CRIRSCO reporting.

Benefits of the joint application of UNFC classification can be summarised as follows:

- **Comprehensive Resource Classification:** UNFC enables the simultaneous evaluation of geothermal energy potential and CRM availability, helping stakeholders understand the interdependencies and co-benefits of integrated projects. For example, brines extracted for geothermal energy may contain economically viable concentrations of lithium or other CRMs.
- **Support for Strategic Planning:** By applying a single, harmonised classification framework, governments and project developers can better align projects with national strategies on raw materials, renewable energy, and climate commitments (e.g., EU Green Deal).
- **Risk Management and De-risking Investments:** UNFC explicitly incorporates uncertainty and ESG-modifying factors in its E, F, and G axes, which helps

identify risks and improves project robustness and investment attractiveness.

- Improved Transparency for Investors: Investors can compare and evaluate different projects more transparently when a common reporting standard is used. This is especially important for hybrid projects where financial viability depends on combined outputs (e.g. electricity + lithium).

Besides the above listed benefits some challenges must be addressed too, when applying the UNFC-tool for coproduction projects:

- Data Integration Complexity: Combining geothermal and CRM resource models requires coordination between disciplines (geology, reservoir engineering, hydrochemistry), which may not be standard practice in existing regulatory or company workflows.
- Timing and Project Maturity Misalignment: Resource classification becomes complex if the geothermal part of a project is in a mature production stage while CRM recovery is still exploratory or conceptual. Such temporal asymmetry affects confidence levels and feasibility ratings in the UNFC matrix.
- Competency and Guidelines Gaps: Standardised guidance for co-extraction is still evolving. Although UNFC provides competency guidelines, practical implementation for joint geothermal-CRM projects may require tailored case studies and training efforts.

When applying UNFC to coproduction projects, we can envision two main scenarios

Scenario A - CRM Extraction Added to an Existing Geothermal Project: In this case, the geothermal system may already have high E and F ratings (e.g., E1, F1), and the G axis for geothermal is mature. When CRM recovery is introduced later:

- Geothermal part: Classified as E1F1G1.
- CRM part: Initially classified as E3F3G4 or E2F2G3 depending on available sampling and feasibility studies.

The UNFC framework allows for maintaining separate but linked classification entries, reflecting different maturity levels. This supports staged investment decisions while preserving overall project integrity.

Scenario B - Joint Project from Inception: When both geothermal and CRM development are launched together, UNFC allows a unified classification from exploration onwards. Shared infrastructure (e.g., wells, reinjection systems) and permitting can be considered in the E-axis evaluation. (Even though separate reports are prepared, the same assessment is included in both of them.) If both

components progress together, their F and G ratings can be aligned, improving project financial feasibility and accelerating timelines.

A joint UNFC assessment also enables operators to define fallback strategies. For instance, if CRM recovery proves economically non-viable, the geothermal operation can continue independently without impairing the overall classification.

UNFC's multi-dimensional approach can effectively support feasibility assessment and financial decision-making. For feasibility analysis this is by systematically addressing technical and socio-economic parameters, including ESG (Environmental, Social, and Governance) factors and technology readiness. For financial evaluation this is by linking resource classification to project maturity and risk level, helping determine when a project is ready for investment or up-scaling and scenario modelling, particularly for direct lithium extraction from geothermal brines, where resource estimation resembles oil & gas practices and benefits from UNFC's compatibility with NI 51-101-type models.

6 JOINT UNFC-ASSESSMENT BASED ON CASE STUDY

The case study area is the fractured granitoid Battonya Complex, located in south-east Hungary (Figure 2). It is significant due to the recent increase in exploration, as it has good thermal conductivity, making it ideal for geothermal exploitation (<http://www.eufire.hu/pages/egs-hungary>). Previous hydrocarbon prospecting has taken place in the area, but this has mainly focused on the weathered margin of the complex (Jancsek et al. 2023). More recently, the extraction of the lithium content of the fluid exploited from the area has become of increasing interest. (<https://hungarytoday.hu/mol-launches-lithium-project-in-south-east-hungary/>).

A hydrodynamic and heat transport model (FEFLOW) was constructed in order to determine the amount of heat that could be extracted. Different scenarios were used for the hydrogeological parameters to determine the uncertainty of extraction. Once the amount of heat had been established, the amount of electricity that could be sold was determined. Then, using the model results, we estimated the amount of recoverable lithium. First, the results of the calculations are presented briefly, followed by a description of the UNFC classification.

6.1 CONCEPT AND CALCULATION OF THE PROJECT

The Battonya Complex (also known as the Battonya High) is surrounded by two large sediment basins: the Makó Trough and the Békés Depression (Figure 2). The location of the planned geothermal system's wells was selected so that the production well would produce water at a temperature of 160°C from a depth of approximately 3,200 metres. The injection well is located within the same fracture

system as the production well, but as far away from it as possible. The temperature of the reinjected water was assumed to be 50°C (Figure 3). Note that the Battonya Complex has not yet been drilled to this depth; the calculations are based on data from shallower wells, deep geophysical measurements, and literature data. The following articles contain the detailed model description and calculation, Kun et al. (2022a, 2022b).

Figure 2: The topography of the Pre-Cenozoic basement surroundings of Battonya High (Kun et al. 2022a).

Figure 3: Hydrostratigraphic units of the Battonya High (Horizontal extent: 70 km, vertical extent: 5 km (Figure 2 shows the section line; the thickness of the layers is not to scale) Legend: 1. Paleozoic metamorphic rocks, granite (Battonya Complex), 2. Lower and Middle Triassic fractured sandstone and dolomite, 3. Middle Miocene conglomerate, 4. Late Miocene conglomerate, 5. Late Miocene aleuritic marl, 6. Late Miocene turbidite, 7. Late Miocene delta sediments, 8. Quaternary formations. (Kun et al. 2022a).

Numerical software that uses both finite difference and finite element methods is widely used to investigate hydrodynamic and heat transfer processes. To solve the present problem, we opted for FEFLOW® finite element software, in which spatial discretisation (mesh generation) plays a key role. The finite element method enables the modelled space to be divided into arbitrary nodes, allowing important areas to be covered with a high mesh density and less important areas with a low mesh density. In hydrodynamic and heat transfer modelling studies, numerous parameters of the modelled rocks and flowing fluid must be specified. However, most of these values are not precisely known. One way to account for uncertainty is to use a Monte Carlo simulation. This method involves using randomly generated values of the measured data instead of the parameters, taking into account the variance of the data. In Monte Carlo estimation, a typical distribution is obtained by performing the calculation many times, at least a thousand times, using a random number generator, and then sorting the solutions by magnitude. However, modelling the 1,000 cases mentioned above with five variable parameters per case would require the creation of an enormous number of models (10^8), which is beyond the scope of modelling capacities. Therefore, we created fuzzy numbers from the parameters and ran the model with these. For any given parameter (e.g. leakage factor), a range can be defined with two extreme values that have a membership value of 0 (an unlikely event), while the most probable value range has a membership value of 1. Connecting these values

produces a fuzzy number that describes the given property (Zadeh, 1965). Plotting this fuzzy number in a rectangular coordinate system produces a triangular or trapezoidal fuzzy number, where the horizontal axis represents the measured parameter and the vertical axis represents the probability. In Figure 4, the range a–d is referred to as the 'support', while the range b–c is referred to as the 'core'. If the values of b and c coincide, the result is a triangular fuzzy number. These ranges are then combined to obtain the fuzzy number with the desired properties.

Figure 4: Trapezoid fuzzy numbers (a); triangular fuzzy numbers (b); (horizontal axis is the measured parameter; vertical axis membership value) (Kun et al. 2022b).

Three models can be run to obtain the total expected spectrum for the smallest, most probable and largest values of a given fuzzy number (for fuzzy triangles, these are the nearest membership values of 0, 1 and 0, respectively). In terms of yields, this meant production of 850, 3000 and 5000 m³/d. The yields were determined such that the depression value would be less than 20 bar for different permeability values, ensuring that operation would still be technically feasible. The models were run in transient mode, with 300 days of production followed by 65 days of maintenance downtime each year throughout an assumed 50-year operating period. This production methodology equates to an annual utilisation rate of 82%, in line with current operating practices (REN21, 2019). Figure 5 shows the simulated temperature distributions for two extreme cases. The worst-case scenario is when small volumes in the model communicate with each other. The best-case scenario is when the volume is four times greater than the previous one. In this case, the distance between the producing and the reinjection well also increases in the model, which significantly reduces the rate of thermal breakthrough. In Hungary, the maximum duration of a geothermal concession is 35 years, and this can be extended once by up to half of the original contract length. Therefore, calculations are generally performed for a period of 35 and 50 years.

Figure 5: Temperature-time diagram showing 50 years of production (5000 m³/d) and 50 years of shutdown under two different scenarios (blue: worst case, orange: best case, L: distance between production and reinjection wells).

According to models based on fuzzy parameter values, the amount of heat that can be extracted at a temperature of 50°C over 35 years, given a certain probability level, is as follows:

- P90: 2.40×10^{15} J
- P50: 7.25×10^{15} J
- P10: 1.126×10^{16} J

6.2 ASSESSMENT OF ELECTRICITY AND HEAT RESOURCES ACCORDING TO THE UNFC CODE

The UNFC supplementary specifications for geothermal energy (UNFC-Geothermal 2022) contain a decision tree for each axis, which greatly assists with classification (Appendix 1, 2, 3). A clear and illustrative proposal for evaluating a heat resource of a given geothermal project was set out by Mijnlieff et al. (2019). This proposal uses a three-axis system of criteria based on the UNFC classification system, arranged in a three-sided rose diagram (Figure 6). This is referred to as the 'project fingerprint'. The evaluation is based on the weakest value of each axis. According to Figure 5, the 'Economic' and 'Internal & external approvals' value on axis E are the weakest (2), so, according to this axis, the referred project is classified as E2.

Figure 6: The referred project's UNFC fingerprint prior to drilling (Mijnlieff et al. 2019)

For the planned geothermal exploitation of new areas such as the Battonya Complex, it is crucial to determine the probability of extracting a given amount of geothermal energy, i.e. the probability of discovery. In Falcone et al. (2022), the Probability of Discovery (PoD) is defined as *'the chance that further exploration, drilling, and well testing of a Potential Geothermal Energy Source will result in the confirmation of a Known Geothermal Energy Source. This will typically be assessed considering the key factors that are required to achieve a discovery which may include temperature, permeability and fluid chemistry or other relevant parameters that are important for the type of Project planned to evaluate the technical feasibility of the Project.'*

6.2.1 G axes – Geothermal resource quantification

When determining the G axis, it must be taken into account that only a few boreholes in the Battonya Complex reached the granite base and even then, they only penetrated it by a few tens of metres. No geothermal fluid production took place from these boreholes either. As the exact depth of the target formation at the project site is unknown, the amount of geothermal energy that can be extracted is primarily based on indirect evidence. This means that the calculated reserves can only be classified as G4 for both heat and electricity production.

To determine how much electricity can be generated based on the three scenarios, we first need to establish how much energy can be converted from the extracted heat into electricity. For the purposes of this calculation, let's assume that our ORC system (Organic Rankine Cycle system) operates at temperatures above 80°C (353 K). The energy above this temperature can be converted into electricity. However, some loss will occur. Since the temperature of the produced water was above 80 °C in all modelled cases and the yield is known, the amount of energy corresponding to temperatures between 50 °C (the temperature of the reinjected water) and 80 °C can be subtracted from the total energy to obtain the amount of thermal energy available for power generation. The amount to be subtracted is only suitable for heat production.

Since the production yield for the P90 case was 850 m³/d, 1.12 × 10¹⁵ J of energy was available for heat production only. For P50, the yield was 3,000 m³/d, so 3.97 × 10¹⁵ J of energy is available for heat production. For P10, with a yield of 5,000 m³/d, 6.62 × 10¹⁵ J is available for heat utilisation only. To obtain the portion of energy suitable for power generation, these values must be subtracted from the total amount of heat extracted (from here on, we will use PJ as the unit of measurement for energy; 1 × 10¹⁵ J = 1 PJ) (Table 1).

Table 1: The total amount of energy extracted and the values suitable for heat utilisation and power generation, according to different probability levels.

Probability level	Total extracted energy [PJ]	Energy for heat only [PJ]	Energy suitable for power generation [PJ]
P90	2.4	1.12	1.28
P50	7.25	3.97	3.28
P10	11.26	6.62	4.64

Since some loss is inevitable when converting thermal energy into electrical energy, the theoretical efficiency of this process is given by Carnot's equation:

$$\eta = \frac{T_1}{T_1 - T_2}$$

η : efficiency

T_1 : absolute temperature of the inlet [K]

T_2 : absolute temperature of the outlet [K]

We determined the theoretical efficiencies using the above equation based on the model data. These were found to be 0.18 for P10, 0.15 for P50 and 0.11 for P90.

However, in practice, these values are generally 10–15% lower, the global average is 12% (Zarrouk and Moon, 2014).

Therefore, we used the values in Table 2 to calculate the amount of electricity that can be generated. Multiplying by the efficiency yielded the amount of electrical energy that can be generated in cases with different probabilities (Table 2).

Table 2: The amount of energy that can be converted into electricity according to different probability levels.

Probability level	Energy suitable for power generation [PJ]	Efficiency	Generate electrical energy. [PJ]
P90	1.28	0.09	0.12
P50	3.28	0.13	0.43
P10	4.64	0.16	0.74

Since the quantity of products associated with the prospective project is estimated mainly on the basis of indirect evidence, the resource can only be of category G4. Based on the above, the calculated heat resources according to the UNFC for the Battonya project's 35-year operating period are as follows:

G4.1: 1.12 PJ; G4.2: 2.85 PJ; G4.3: 2.65 PJ

The calculated electricity resources according to the UNFC for the Battonya project's 35-year operating period are as follows

G4.1: 0.12 PJ; G4.2: 0.31 PJ; G4.3: 0.31 PJ

6.2.2 E axes – Heat resource evaluation

Projects in the preparatory phase for which no implementation has yet occurred in the given reservoir, like in this case, can only be classified as category E3. As the economic viability of geothermal heat production in the Battonya-High region cannot yet be determined, despite a study on geothermal heat production having already been conducted, it is classified as category **E3.2** due to insufficient information.

6.2.3 F axes – Heat resource evaluation

In the area under investigation, the feasibility of heat extraction cannot be assessed due to limited technical data and the fact that the target formation has not yet been explored. Therefore, it belongs to category 3 on the F axis. Although

regional geological studies in the research area indicate favourable geothermal conditions, there are no studies specific to this location. Therefore, the final classification is category **F3.3**.

6.2.4 E axes – Electricity resource evaluation

Projects in the preparatory phase for which no implementation has yet occurred in the given reservoir, like in this case, can only be classified as category E3. Although the environmental-socio-economic viability of geothermal energy production in the Battonya-High region can be determined on the basis of realistic future assumptions, it is currently considered that there are no reasonable prospects of economic viability in the foreseeable future. This is because, under current market conditions in Hungary, the revenue generated from electricity production does not cover the cost of production. Therefore, it is classified as category **E3.3**.

6.2.5 F axes – Electricity resource evaluation

In the area under investigation, the feasibility of geothermal power production cannot be assessed due to limited technical data and the fact that the target formation has not yet been explored. Therefore, it belongs to category 3 on the F axis. Although regional geological studies in the research area indicate favourable geothermal conditions, there are no studies specific to this location. Therefore, the final classification is category **F3.3**.

6.3 JOINT EVALUATION OF ELECTRICITY AND HEAT RESOURCES ACCORDING TO THE UNFC CODE

The combined categorisation of heat and electricity generation by viable, potentially viable, non-viable and prospective projects is illustrated in Figure 7. Whilst the UNFC standard classes are characterised by a high level of detail with regard to working or thoroughly explored viable projects, as they allow a distinction between projects that have been approved for development, those that are under construction and those that are in operation, there is no such distinction for exploration of early-stage (not yet drilled) prospective projects, which all fall in one class (Falcone et al. 2025).

UNFC Classes Defined by Categories and Sub-categories						
Total Products	Produced	Sold or used production				
		Production which is unused or consumed in operation				
	Class	Sub-class	Categories			
			E	F	G	
Known Sources	Viable Projects	On Production	1	1.1	1, 2, 3	
		Approved for Development	1	1.2	1, 2, 3	
		Justified for Development	1	1.3	1, 2, 3	
	Potentially Viable Projects	Development Pending	2 ^b	2.1	1, 2, 3	
		Development On Hold	2	2.2	1, 2, 3	
	Non-Viable Projects	Development Unclassified	3.2	2.2	1, 2, 3	
		Development Not Viable	3.3	2.3	1, 2, 3	
	Remaining products not developed from identified projects		3.3	4	1, 2, 3	
Potential Sources	Prospective projects	(No sub-classes Defined)	3.2	3	4	
	Remaining products not developed from prospective projects		3.3	4	4	

Figure 7: UNFC classes and sub-classes to present combined or regional portfolio assessments (Falcone et al. 2025).

In the case of the Battonya project under study, we mentioned that there is no productive drilling yet. As illustrated in Figure 7, the project under consideration is classified as a 'Prospective Project' in terms of its heat resource, while the category of energy resources is designated as 'Remaining Products not developed from Prospective Projects'.

A fundamental question for the entire project is the extent of the fractured geothermal reservoir and whether it can be stimulated to achieve higher yields and greater spacing between the producing well and reinjection, for avoiding thermal breakthrough. The biggest challenge for heat production is the insufficient size of the heat market, given that there are currently no major heat users in the region. With regard to the generation of power, the cooling demand can be met by air cooling, since there is neither surface nor ground water in the area. This suggests that the efficiency of power generation will be diminished during the summer months.

It is anticipated that an agricultural or industrial entity will establish itself in the area. Industrial users sometimes require elevated temperatures of around 150°C for specific manufacturing processes, such as tyre production. In this case, the potential for increased electricity generation loss and the financial burden of

investing in a generator unit can be mitigated. The same applies to agricultural users wanting to use the higher-temperature fluid for absorption cooling.

The geothermal project under discussion is a prospective project. The classification of heat resource according to the UNCF is: **G4.1: 1.12 PJ; G4.2: 2.85 PJ; G4.3: 2.65 PJ;**

and in the case of electricity resource is: **G4.1: 0.12 PJ; G4.2: 0.31 PJ; G4.3: 0.31 PJ**

7 ASSESSMENT OF LITHIUM RESOURCES ACCORDING TO THE UNFC CODE

Several methods are used to evaluate mineral resources, including the CRIRSCO-aligned reporting codes PERC (<https://percstandard.org/>, for projects reporting to European stock-exchanges) and JORC (<https://www.jorc.org>, for projects reporting in the Asian-Pacific region). However, these codes only report on 'viable' projects, thus providing a selective picture from a strategic resource management perspective. Nevertheless, they are crucial for stock market reporting. In order to integrate societal and environmental considerations, as well as the necessary technological feasibility assessments, into inventory assessment and extend it to non-viable resources, the uniform application of UNFC worldwide has become essential. In order to avoid having to prepare two assessments, a 'bridging' document was developed (UNECE, 2024; see CRM-geothermal Deliverable D4.1; Falck & Correia, 2025). Another advantage of the UNFC is that it enables joint assessment in cases of combined geothermal energy and mineral production, which is important in the context of CRM-geothermal. But there is a key difference between traditional mineral resource calculations and calculations of mineral resources that can be extracted from geothermal fluids. In the latter case, the volume of the mineral raw material cannot be clearly defined a priori. The underlying reason is, that its extraction depends on the yield and concentration of the produced fluid, which could vary over time. Although the classification of oil and gas resources is much closer to our goals, the UNFC classification of hydrocarbons does not yet fully apply to the extraction of ore from liquids. (Figure 8). This is particularly true of petrothermal reservoir systems, where insufficient fluid is present and must be added and circulated artificially. The in situ leaching period only lasts a few days or weeks. In contrast, the time available for fluid-rock interaction in hydrothermal cases is measured on a geological timescale. In these cases, it is also important to consider when the reinjected water reaches the production well. Even if thermal breakthrough does not occur, the lithium concentration of the reinjected water is significantly lower than that of water that has been in the reservoir for thousands of years (Figure 9). However, in addition to thermodynamic processes, kinetic processes must also be taken into account. The concentration of lithium may exceed the reinjection value through the following processes: a) mixing/dilution with groundwater in the area; b)

dissolution of minerals covering the cracks. Since the extent of these processes varies over time, a kinetic component can be added to the calculations (see CRM-geothermal D2.4 report). As Vu et al. (2013) pointed out in their study of lithium leaching kinetics, the solution can become saturated with lithium relatively quickly under special circumstances, even faster than the water heats up.

Figure 8: Volumetric delineation of various raw materials. A) Ore body; B) Hydrocarbon deposit; C) Subsurface complex flow system in ore rock.

Figure 9: Flowpath and simulated travel time in case of a geothermal dublet (Kun et al. 2022b).

In the simulated case shown in Figure 9, it takes around 5 years for water to reach the production well from the reinjection well, accounting for 40% of the production well's yield. This means that, after at least five years, the lithium concentration in the produced fluid should decrease. As no laboratory experiments had been conducted to examine the dissolution kinetics of lithium in the area under investigation, the following assumptions were made. In the worst-case scenario, we calculated a 30% decrease in lithium concentration in the produced fluid after five years. In the best-case scenario, the concentration would remain unchanged. In the intermediate scenario, the concentration decreased by 10% after five years. Although modelling can be used to estimate the time and flow rate at which the reinjected water reaches the production well with relative accuracy, it is much more difficult to determine changes in lithium or other compound concentrations in the fluid, since the kinetics of the leaching process are less well understood.

Pugh et al. (2023) published a white paper on the methodology for estimating reserves from brine mining, drawing on their experience in the oil industry. In this white paper, the original in-place quantity used to estimate lithium reserves is referred to as Original Lithium In Place, (OLIP), which represents the total volume present in the subsurface. The producible lithium reserves are referred to as "Producible Lithium In Place" (PLIP), which represents the total amount that can be transported to the factory for processing. The final recoverable quantity, referred to as "Recoverable Lithium In Place," takes into account losses during the processing stage and represents the total quantity available for sale. During the evaluation, they also determine the various lithium reserves based on hydrogeological parameters. It is therefore appropriate to use hydrodynamic and transport modelling to determine recoverable lithium reserves (PLIP).

7.1.1 G axes – Lithium resource quantification

The lithium content of the rock-forming minerals in the studied area of the Battonyai Complex (Jancsek et al., 2023) was examined in detail. The main Li-bearing minerals in the area are biotite and muscovite, with concentrations of up to ~3,800 and ~2,500 ppm, respectively. The high Li content of the geothermal waters in the study area could be explained by the chloritisation of biotite. However, only a few water samples are available to determine the lithium content, with values ranging from 70 to 140 ppm. These values have not yet been confirmed in an official report.

As the quantity of lithium that could be extracted (PLIP) from the proposed project can only be estimated using indirect evidence, the resource can only be categorised as G4. Based on model calculations, the lithium resources for the 35-year operating period of the Battonya project, calculated according to the UNFC, are as follows (for pure lithium in tons):

G4.1: 625 t;**G4.2: 1 889 t;****G4.3: 2 736 t**

7.1.2 E axes – Lithium resource evaluation

Projects in the preparatory phase that have not yet been implemented can only be classified as E3, not only in the area under review, but anywhere in the world. On the basis of realistic assumptions of future conditions, it is currently considered that there are no reasonable prospects for environmental-socio-economic viability in the foreseeable future. Therefore, it is classified as category **E3.3**.

7.1.3 F axes – Lithium resource evaluation

In the area under investigation, the feasibility of fluid production cannot be assessed due to limited technical data and the fact that the target formation has not yet been explored. Even the technology necessary is under active development, following successful pilot studies, but has yet to be demonstrated to be technically feasible for this project. Therefore, the final classification is category **F4.1**.

8 CONCLUSIONS

Overall, the preliminary studies of the Battonya Complex project suggest that further data collection or research is required to evaluate the potential feasibility or development. One of the most important things to examine is how quickly the minerals lining the fractures dissolve, i.e. the process's kinetics under reservoir conditions. The technology necessary is under active development, following successful pilot studies, but has yet to be demonstrated to be technically feasible for this project. On the basis of realistic assumptions of future conditions, it is currently considered that there are no reasonable prospects for economic viability in the foreseeable future. All product quantity associated with this Project, estimated or postulated primarily on indirect evidence.

In general, hydrodynamic and transport modelling are appropriate tools for the overall evaluation of the multiple projects according to the UNFC code. The joint assessment must be based on the value of each commodity, which is calculated separately according to its UNFC code. However, it must also assess the environmental, social and technical feasibility of all products. In all cases, the weakest category should be considered the common value. From an economic point of view, it should be considered whether the project as a whole can still be considered economically viable if the production of heat and electricity alone makes it viable, despite the uneconomic nature of lithium production.

It is important to note that large datasets, particularly those from hydrocarbon research, facilitate the application of a wide range of machine learning methods. This is particularly true of comprehensive petrophysical datasets and traditional geostatistical methods that were previously carried out using them. As the calculation of recoverable geothermal energy is similar to that in the hydrocarbon industry in many respects, a breakthrough in the application of machine learning is expected soon.

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APPENDIX 1: E-AXIS DECISION TREE (UNFC-GEOTHERMAL, 2022)

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